

LARKIN TURNER b. Jun-Aug 1778 [ws] d. 23 Feb 1878 Meriwether, GA [v]. The Comprehensive Genealogical Records and Resolution of a Brick Wall Ancestor (1.0)

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ABSTRACT

Genealogists frequently encounter a brick wall in researching ancestors where lack of records, destruction of documents, and lack of all living memory make tracing lineage seem an impossibility. LARKIN TURNER was one such ancestor, being the 5th and 4th great-grandfather of the authors, respectively. Through the use of modern (2025) technology and techniques the authors present the full and comprehensive genealogical records of LARKIN TURNER to date, which includes parentage, siblings, and early life in Georgia, and all uncertain future works. This method and validation includes autosomal and sex DNA, statistical relationships to related families, Artificial Intelligence (A.I.), online resource repository utility, and traditional brute-force reading of 19th century script in digitized microfilms. The key process involved using A.I. and statistical methods to identify likely parentage candidates and geographic areas, and then developing postulates to test with more traditional means. Finally, our process highlights the strength of utilizing multiple colleagues as part of the research process, especially the complementary synergy of differing generations of researchers utilizing their experience and skills.

Cite as:

Turner, E. L., & Turner, M. M. (2025). LARKIN TURNER b. Jun-Aug 1778 [ws] d. 23 Feb 1878 Meriwether, GA [v]. The Comprehensive Genealogical Records and Resolution of a Brick Wall Ancestor (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17087283>

NOTATION CONVENTIONS

Not Investigated [ni] : A fact or citation recorded but not yet researched or evaluated. No GPS elements applied. Serves as a marker for future work.

Verified [v] : A confident conclusion that meets all five GPS elements: exhaustive research, complete and accurate citations, thorough analysis and correlation of evidence, resolution of conflicting evidence, and a soundly reasoned, coherently written conclusion.

Well-Supported [ws] : A strong conclusion where four of the five GPS elements are satisfied, but one remains pending—typically either exhaustive research or conflict resolution. The evidence is highly persuasive but not yet fully proven.

Probable [pr] : Multiple independent sources support the same conclusion, but 2–3 GPS elements are incomplete. Correlation and citations exist, yet the research may not be exhaustive or conflicts may not be resolved.

Possible [ps] : A working hypothesis supported by minimal or indirect evidence. Typically only 1–2 GPS elements are met, such as a single source or weak correlation. Used as a marker for ongoing research.

Uncertain [u] : A claim mentioned without adequate evidence. Zero to one GPS elements are satisfied; citations may be missing or unreliable. Serves as a placeholder until stronger documentation is found.

Refuted [r] : A previously asserted fact proven false. Conflicting evidence has been resolved against the claim, and citations clearly document the refutation. This status preserves an audit trail so future researchers do not repeat the error.

I. INTRODUCTION

I want to begin this paper by recognizing my uncle, Michael “Mike” Miller Turner, who has been our family’s historian for decades. His journey mirrors the experiences of many genealogists working in the late 20th and early 21st centuries. When he first began, even his grandfather — my great-grandfather, ERNEST ALFRED TURNER — did not know the name of his own grandfather, LEVI JOHN WOOTEN TURNER. Through years of determination and patient digging, Uncle Mike pieced together the family’s lineage back to LARKIN TURNER as follows:

LARKIN TURNER d. 23 Feb 1878 Meriwether, GA [v]¹

HIRAM TURNER b. 22 Aug 1812 Baldwin Co. GA [v] d. 20 Dec 1864 Hickory Level, Carroll, GA. [v]

LEVI JOHN WOOTEN TURNER b. 11 Aug 1835 Carroll Co., GA [v] d. 3 May 1915 Nacogdoches, TX [v].

JOSEPH BENJAMIN TURNER b. 30 Jul 1866 Carroll Co. GA [v] d. 12 Jan 1929 Garrison, Nacogdoches, TX [v]

ERNEST ALFRED TURNER b. 22 Jun 1895 Garrison, Nacogdoches, TX [v] d. 11 Jun 1956 Premont, Jim Wells, TX [v]

Larkin’s parentage has long been a “brick wall” in our family research. Records from the early 19th century are scarce, and many were lost to courthouse fires and the Civil War. For decades, this lack of documentation left us with only fragments and guesses.

But the widespread digitization and indexing of historical records in the early 21st century finally opened new doors. My uncle and I were able to piece together a much clearer picture of Larkin’s later life, his children, and the circumstances of his death. For example, newspapers in Georgia frequently reported on him in his later years, fascinated by his vitality and extreme age claims. These articles, alongside county records, confirmed beyond doubt that he died on 23 February 1878 in Meriwether County, Georgia [v]¹.

In addition to records, Uncle Mike turned to DNA testing in the 2000s. He took part in both autosomal testing (through Ancestry.com and 23andMe) and Y-chromosome testing (Y-37, Y-67, Y-111, and Big Y). The Y-DNA results, published through the Turner DNA Project {1}, placed our ancestry within the “Teal Group 5” {2}. This group includes participants whose lines likely connect back to a set of three Turner families who leased land in Virginia from PETER HEDGMAN in the mid-1700s.

These DNA results were a turning point. Combined with the paper trail, they firmly link our branch of the family to LARKIN TURNER and all his known children. The autosomal testing has been equally valuable: as of today, there are 115 autosomal DNA matches on Ancestry.com that connect to Larkin and his children (see Table 1). These matches include multiple third- and fourth-cousin relationships, which provide genetic confirmation of what the historical records suggest. With this lineage established, the next challenge was addressing the long-standing uncertainty around LARKIN TURNER’s parentage.

Prior to this study, there was no firm knowledge of LARKIN TURNER’s early life or parentage. The prevailing theory in online community trees has been that LARKIN was a son of JAMES TURNER [r]⁹ b. 1753 d. 1806 and REBECCA HAMNER [r]⁹ b. 1753 d. 1808. However, the will of JAMES TURNER⁹ makes no mention of LARKIN, which is a major inconsistency in this proposed linkage. The common explanation offered is that because LARKIN was born around 1770, he was already well-established by the time of the will and therefore not named. Another possibility is that LARKIN was a child from a prior marriage, or perhaps from a different mother altogether.

These kinds of community tree assumptions spread like a virus, replicated and repeated over time. Even we are not immune to this problem: well-intentioned notes or provisional data often get picked up and re-shared by new researchers. For example, my uncle Mike once created the Find-a-Grave entry for LARKIN TURNER¹². That entry was based on a single line from a genealogical publication {3}. Yet, despite no headstone or graveyard ever being located for LARKIN, this entry continues to be widely cited as if it were an authoritative record of his birth and death. To move beyond these conflicting and sometimes unreliable community records, we turned to a structured research process that combined both traditional methods and modern tools.

Child of LARKIN TURNER	DNA Matches
TABITHA TURNER b. 1801 d. 1838 [v]	2
LAVINIA TURNER b. 1805 d. 1880 [v]	7
RILEY FLETCHER TURNER b. 1807 d. 1884 [v]	2
ALLETHIA TURNER b. 1809 d. 1884 [v]	10
EMILY TURNER b. 1810 d. 1849 [v]	1
HIRAM TURNER b. 1812 d. 1864 [v]	55
ELIZABETH H TURNER b. 1813 d. 1904 [v]	1
LARKIN LEE TURNER b. 1816 d. 1871 [v]	12
MARTHA LOURANIE TURNER b. 1818 d. 1857 [v]	12
ELEANOR LEAH TURNER b. 1820 d. 1855 [v]	12
SARAH TURNER b. 1824 d. 1889 [v]	12
LEAH ELEANOR TURNER b. 1826 d. 1856 [v]	12

Table 1. Children of LARKIN TURNER and number of DNA matches on Ancestry.com from August 25, 2025.

II. METHODS AND DISCOVERY NARRATIVE

I have been an active family genealogist since the mid-2000s. Alongside my uncle, Michael Miller Turner, I've continued our family's research into the next generation. I also work closely with my aunt, Annmarie Kolodziej, to preserve her work on my matriarchal families of KRIEG and WALTER, both of Swiss origin.

In the summer of 2025, Uncle Mike and I renewed our enthusiasm for tackling some of our long-standing ancestral brick walls, this time using up-to-date technology and the wide availability of AI tools. Preliminary exercises with ChatGPT 4.0 proved fruitful for conducting 'deep searches' of digital records, identifying keywords, building narrative hypotheses about life events, and locating repositories for further research.

As part of this testing, we compiled all known census records for LARKIN TURNER by uploading screenshots into AI for transcription and long-term reference. This produced a complete set of transcribed census records from 1810 [r]⁶, 1820 [v]⁷, 1830 [v]⁸, 1840 [v]⁹, 1850 [v]¹⁰, 1860 [v]¹¹, and 1870 [v]¹². With these census transcriptions in place, we began our analysis by testing them against each other to determine the most accurate possible birth year for LARKIN TURNER.

IIA. BIRTH OF LARKIN TURNER

First, I asked AI to correlate all dependents and their ages across each census record according to the

authoritative record (Table 1). With one exception, all census records matched both the names and the reported ages (or reasonable age ranges) of each dependent. The exception was the 1810 census in Culpeper, VA [r]⁶. In that case, both the number of household members and their ages failed to match any of the known data for 1810. The VA 1810 census listed extra individuals of multiple ages while also omitting dependents who were known to be alive and living at home at that time. This evidence was sufficient to determine that the census refers to a different LARKIN TURNER, and is therefore refuted [r]

Through this exercise another glaring inconsistency emerged. LARKIN's reported year of birth was consistently ~1778 or 1779 in every census, except in the 1870¹² census where he reported being 100 years old, which implied a birth year of 1770. That 1770 date has since become the commonly accepted birth year in many community trees. However, this rests on a single census entry. In addition, numerous newspaper articles and reprints (more than fifteen in total) discussed LARKIN's advanced age in the years following 1870 until his death in 1878. A small sampling of these articles demonstrates the exaggerated, almost celebratory language surrounding his supposed vitality:

Mr. Larkin Turner, aged 110 years, died February 23, 1878. He, like the patriarchs of old, waited for death "having set his house in order." When he felt the approach of death he settled himself firmly in his chair (refusing to lie down), and died sitting erect, and without a struggle. He retained his senses to the last moment, and died from no disease—nature exhausted. During his long life he had but one short attack of fever, having never taken a dose of medicine until that time, which was about the time he was 100 years of age. This he told us himself.

— Meriwether Vindicator ¹³

My suspicions about LARKIN's age claim were confirmed after encountering this striking example in an 1874 article:

MR. LARKIN TURNER, of Meriwether county, has been sojourning in these low grounds of sorrow just one hundred and four years, and has never had the toothache or missed a meal on account of sickness. Three of his sisters were one hundred years of age when they died, and his grandfather one hundred and twenty-six.

— Georgia Weekly Telegraph ¹⁴

After conducting another round of literary searches and AI prompting, I found there was a cultural phenomenon in the 1870s that indulged in stories of longevity and age. In fact, the temptation to inflate one's age was often encouraged {3, 4, 5}. This was especially convenient in the post-Civil War South, where many records simply did not exist to refute such claims—and in LARKIN's case, from his earlier life in the post-Revolutionary period, the documentary record was already thin. The articles cited above ^{13, 14} highlight how exaggerated claims were celebrated and how language was inflated for readership.

My own summation is that LARKIN reported his age accurately in every census until 1870. It is unknown whether he exaggerated his age before that year, but I find it suspicious that he told the census taker he was exactly 100 years old in 1870. My hypothesis is that LARKIN invented this claim at the very moment of speaking to the enumerator, and then simply continued to embellish the story in

subsequent years. The final telling point is that LARKIN increased his claimed age more than once: near the end of his life he reported being 110 years old ¹³, which would place his birth in 1768.

To establish a more precise range for his birth, I performed a final analysis of LARKIN’s census records, charting the reported ages against the known dates of enumeration. This analysis yielded a likely birth between 6 July 1778 and 17 October 1778. Based on the consistency of the 1850 and 1860 census records, the most probable birth window falls between June and August 1778.

Census Year	Census Date	Age Category	Birth Year Range	Notes
1820	07 Aug 1820	45	≤ Aug 7, 1775	Broad
1830	01 Jun 1830	50–59	Jun 2, 1770 – Jun 1, 1780	Supports 1778
1840	01 Jun 1840	60–69	Jun 2, 1770 – Jun 1, 1780	Supports 1778
1850	01 Jun 1850	72	Jun 2, 1777 – Jun 1, 1778	Tight window
1860	01 Jun 1860	81	Jun 2, 1778 – Jun 1, 1779	Tight window

Table 2. LARKIN TURNER census record reported age based on date.

Therefore, we conclude that LARKIN TURNER was born in 1778 at the well-supported [ws] level, and further refined to June–August 1778 at the probable [pr] level. Having established a reliable birth year, the next step was to search exhaustively for records that might place LARKIN in Georgia during his early adulthood and provide clues to his parentage.

IIB. EXHAUSTIVE RECORDS SEARCH AND POSTULATE FORMULATION

Having established that LARKIN TURNER was born in 1778 rather than 1770, and that the supposed parentage link to JAMES TURNER and REBECCA HAMNER could no longer be considered valid, I next undertook an exhaustive records search. My goal was to review every available record from the late 1700s through 1820 that could shed light on LARKIN’s early life and parentage in Georgia.

For this effort, I drew on a wide range of resources, both digital and archival. These included Newspapers.com {6}, the Georgia Archives {7} and Virtual Vault {8}, FamilySearch.org {9}, and the Georgia Historical Newspapers project {10}. In addition, I performed targeted “deep searches” with AI tools to uncover overlooked mentions, scattered references, or patterns that might not appear in standard indexes.

This exercise yielded multiple references to LARKIN TURNER in Georgia in the late 1700s and early 1800s. The exhaustive listing of these items and their respective validations is provided in Section III; however, the most notable examples to discuss here are:

- [ws] March 25, 1796: JAMES TURNER of Hancock County sells 85 acres in Hancock County, Georgia, on the waters of Little Ogeechee to WYATT EASON for 15 pounds sterling. Witnessed by LARKIN TURNER and JACOB LEFTWICH, J.P. ¹⁵ Appendix A.

- [ps] *State v. LARKIN TURNER, September 1796: In Hancock County, LARKIN TURNER was indicted for a misdemeanor charge of bastardy, meaning he was accused of fathering a child out of wedlock. The grand jury issued a True Bill, but the prosecution later entered a nolle prosequi, almost certainly indicating a private settlement or dropped charges.* ¹⁶ Appendix B.

- [v] December 25, 1802: Witness, along with WILLIAM DRISKELL, providing a \$300 security bond in probate for LEVINAH EVANS, administratrix for the estate of ISAAC EVANS, deceased, in Hancock County. ¹⁷

We were immediately able to validate the 1802 probate witness entry, as WILLIAM DRISKELL was LARKIN's father-in-law. This would have taken place after his marriage to ELEANOR LEAH and the birth of TABITHA ^{b. 1801 d. 1838} [v]. This record firmly places our LARKIN in Hancock County at an early point in the 1800s. It also highlights that LARKIN was a person of means, since he was able to provide bond for the probate.

The court case is an intriguing find and deserves more research. According to the court minutes ¹⁶, it involved a LARKIN TURNER accused of conceiving a child out of wedlock. This does fit within the time frame, as LARKIN would have been around 18 at the time, and it is very close to the supposed marriage to ELEANOR LEAH in 1798 [ps]. To validate this record, a researcher would need to examine the full court records in person at Morrow, Georgia. Interestingly, another court record is listed in 1805 for a LARKIN TURNER, which also requires further investigation. ¹⁸

Finally, we located a 1796 deed record for JAMES TURNER, where a LARKIN TURNER is listed as the primary witness. It would follow that this LARKIN TURNER was the son of JAMES TURNER, as a son was typically chosen as the primary witness in a deed action. Originally, we marked this as [ps] when evaluating possible parentage, since it could have referred to a different LARKIN and a different family. Subsequently, this record is now treated as [ws], given the confirmed parentage.

Taken together, these records place LARKIN TURNER in Hancock County during the 1790s and early 1800s and confirm his ties by marriage and witness roles. Yet, despite their importance, these documents alone could not resolve the larger question of LARKIN's parentage. To address that gap, I turned next to the statistical evidence available through the Turner DNA database. The documentary trail was suggestive but incomplete; therefore, we complemented it with genetic evidence from the Turner DNA Project.

IIC. TREATMENT OF TURNER DNA TREES AND CANDIDATE FATHERS

For this stage of analysis, I turned to the Turner DNA Project database and the Teal Group 5 participant trees {5} to assemble possible parents of LARKIN TURNER. To do this, I first normalized all submitted lineage data and entered it into Excel. I then standardized birth and death dates across the data and created a system of identifiers using each ancestor's first name and birth year—for example, "larkin1778."

To help compare and contrast the trees, I labeled each one by its earliest known ancestor. This provided a consistent reference point for distinguishing one tree from another. Where trees overlapped and contained identical lineages, I merged them into a single composite tree.

After collating all of the data by hand for more than 100 individuals, I used ChatGPT 4.0 to generate a

matplotlib graphic that plotted the earliest ancestors born prior to 1810 on a single chart. The X-axis represents birth year, and each ancestor's birth location is also displayed. To highlight generational timing, I shaded the graphic to indicate the typical childbearing years of 20–50.

Finally, I added a vertical line at LARKIN TURNER's 1778 birth year. This simple visual allowed me to identify which individuals fell within the possible range to have been his father (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Pre-1810 Turner Ancestors and their possible parentage of 1778 LARKIN TURNER

Using this method, I was able to narrow the pool of possible candidate fathers for LARKIN TURNER to the following individuals: JamesJr1742, JohnM1746, Alexander1741, George1755, JamesSr1730, JamesJr1758, and JohnRWS1750. With the candidate fathers narrowed to this group, the final process was to build a hypothetical picture of LARKIN TURNER by combining the results of the exhaustive record search with the statistical analysis of these lineages, and then evaluating each candidate father in turn.

IID. FINAL DISCOVERY PROCESS

With the candidate fathers identified, I developed a working hypothesis of LARKIN TURNER's early life. Based on the cumulative evidence, LARKIN was likely born outside of Georgia in the summer of 1778 and moved with his parents to Georgia—most probably to the Hancock County region—in the late 1700s. His family appears to have been people of some means, possessing land, property, and at least modest financial resources. By 1800, LARKIN was married, established as head of household in Hancock County, and holding property of his own.

We next turned to the candidate fathers. Given the 1776 deed record where a LARKIN TURNER witnessed a transaction involving JAMES TURNER, we postulated that there was a strong chance one of the men named James was his father. Initial leads seemed promising, as one LARKIN was indeed listed as a child in a Turner family tree. However, further research showed that this individual later moved to Alabama and died there, eliminating him as our ancestor. Because our LARKIN came from a family of

means, we then focused on exhaustively searching probate wills in adjacent Georgia counties, looking for a JAMES TURNER who died between the 1810s and 1830s in a way that aligned with both the historical record and the DNA profiles.

This effort yielded a pivotal result: the will of JAMES TURNER, probated 28 February 1826 in Morgan County, Georgia, names a LARKIN TURNER specifically¹⁹ [v], offering the most direct documentary link to his paternal heritage to date.

Finally, to validate this finding, we searched the Turner Teal Group trees for the names of all the potential siblings of LARKIN listed in the will. We were able to match these individuals to participant DNA trees through WADE HAMPTON TURNER b.1786 d.1865. This firmly established that our LARKIN was indeed named in the 28 February 1826 Morgan County will of JAMES TURNER¹⁹ and directly linked him to other Y-DNA testers.

Therefore, we conclude that LARKIN TURNER b. 1778 d. 1878 was the son of JAMES TURNER b. 1759 d. 1826 and ELIZABETH JANE BAKER b. 1765 d. 1826 [v].

Subsequently, introducing the siblings of LARKIN TURNER into ancestry.com and testing for autosomal DNA matches yields the following results for additional validation (Table 3).

Table 3. The siblings of LARKIN TURNER and autosomal DNA matches on ancestry.com in September, 2025.

Sibling of LARKIN TURNER	DNA MATCHES
ALLEN TURNER b.1786 d. 1866 [v]	6
WADE HAMPTON TURNER b.1786 d.1865 [v]	8
GREEN BERRY TURNER b.1787 d.1869 [v]	1
EASOM TURNER b.1789 d.1824 [v]	2
SUSAN E. TURNER b.1789 d.1878 [v]	1
WILLIAM A F TURNER b.1790 d.1856 [v]	7
JAMES BARTON TURNER b.1793 d.1860 [v]	2
SAMUEL TURNER b.1795 d.1851 [v]	1
SELETA ELIZABETH TURNER b.1799 d.1878 [v]	1

Taken together, the following genealogical summary in the rest of this paper consolidates the validated events of LARKIN TURNER's life, with each entry marked by its respective evidence level and noted areas for future works.

III. GENEALOGICAL TIMELINE OF LARKIN TURNER b. 1778[ws] d. 23 Feb 1878 Meriwether, GA [v]

Table 4. Full Genealogical Timeline of LARKIN TURNER

Date and Validation	Event
c. Jun–Aug 1778 [ws]	Estimated birth of LARKIN TURNER, refined from census records in this work.
c. Jun–Aug 1778 [pr]	Born in South Carolina. ^{10,11}
c. Jun–Aug 1778 [ps]	Born in Virginia. ¹²
c. Jun–Aug 1778 [v]	Born to JAMES TURNER <small>b. 1759 d. 1826</small> and ELIZABETH JANE BAKER <small>b. 1765 d. 1826</small>
25 Mar 1796 [ws]	Witness to deed: JAMES TURNER of Hancock Co. sold 85 acres on Little Ogeechee to WYATT EASON; witnessed by LARKIN TURNER and JACOB LEFTWICH, J.P. ¹⁵
Sep 1796 [ps]	<i>State v. LARKIN TURNER, Hancock Co.</i> ; indicted for bastardy, case later dismissed by <i>nolle prosequi</i> . ¹⁶
06 Nov 1802 [ps]	Listed as defaulter in Capt. BULLOCK's district in Hancock County. ²²
25 Dec 1802 [v]	LARKIN TURNER and WILLIAM DRISKELL posted \$300 probate bond for LEVINAH EVANS, administratrix of the estate of ISAAC EVANS, Hancock Co. ¹⁷
Feb 1805 [ps]	<i>State v. LARKIN TURNER, Hancock Co.</i> ¹⁸
1805 [ps]	Georgia Land Lotto – Single entry. Registered but not fortunate drawer. ²⁰
1807 [u]	Not listed in fortunate drawers transcription for 1807 land lotto. Need to verify by hand and look at the entries. ³³
1812 [pr]	LARKIN TURNER, Serv. Org. 27009 [Capt. Wilson's Co., Ga. Mil]. ²⁵
1812 [u]	LARKIN TURNER, 1st Regiment Mississippi Territorial Volunteers [Brig. Gen. F. L. CLAIRBORNE, Col. COWLES MEAD, Col. JOSPEH CARSON]. ²¹
7 Aug 1820 [v]	U.S. census, Jasper Co., GA, lists household of LARKIN TURNER. ⁷

- 21 Nov 1820 [pr] Listed as fortunate drawer in the newspaper for Land Lottery for Jasper County. ³²
- 28 Feb 1826 [v] Will of JAMES TURNER, Morgan Co., GA, names LARKIN TURNER as heir. ¹⁹ Appendix B.
- 13 Nov 1827 [ps] One bay MARE eight or nine years old, and COLT, and ten barrels of CORN—levied on as the property of LARKIN TURNER, to satisfy a Fieri Facias in favor of E. & L. M'MICHAEL versus said TURNER. Multiple Reprints. Butt's Co. ²⁹
- 14 Jan 1828 [ps] One sorrel FILLY, about two years old, levied on as the property of LARKIN TURNER, to satisfy a Fi. Fa. in favor of E. & S. McMICHEAL, vs. said LARKIN TURNER. Butt's Co. With multiple reprints. ²⁸
- 1830 [v] U.S. census, Carroll Co., GA, lists household of LARKIN TURNER. ⁸
- 1832 [pr] Carroll Co. tax digest lists LARKIN TURNER as a defaulter in Captain WHISINHUNT's district in Carroll County. ³⁶
- 1832 [r] Cherokee Land Lottery, Crawford's District, Morgan Co., lists a LARKIN TURNER; 110 8th District, 2nd Section, Cherokee. ²⁴
- 21 May 1835 [r] LARKIN TURNER and ELISHA TURNER's interest in 100¼ acres of land, being the East half of lot No. 38, in the fifteenth district of originally Monroe now Upson, whereon LARKIN TURNER now lives, to satisfy sundry fi fas issuing from 537th dist. G. M. in favor. Multiple reprints in later issues. ²⁶
- 1836 [r] Georgia Tax Roll. Captain HAYNES's District. Harris Co. Line1: [1 1 202½ ... 202 20 Hab] line2: [160 ... 110 8 2 Section] pg(slave rolls) [4 66 5½ Turner] ³⁷
- 11 Jan 1839 [u] Missing Promissory Note from LARKIN TURNER from PHILIP LAMAR made payable to WADE TOMLINSON for five dollars. Muscogee County. Multiple Reprints. ³¹
- 1840 [v] U.S. census, District 649, Carroll Co., GA, lists household of LARKIN TURNER. ⁹
- 1842 [v] Georgia Tax Roll. District 649, Carroll Co. Listed as defaulter, owning 202 acres. ³⁸

08 Mar 1842 [r]	LARKIN TURNER vs SARAH TURNER divorce announcement in Newton. Multiple Reprints. ³⁵
1847 [v]	Georgia Tax Roll. District 6, Number 649, Carroll Co. NO slaves, 202 total acres, 101 first quality, 101 second quality, no. district 586, Ga. \$491 total property. Note – HIRAM TURNER on next line. ³⁹
1850 [v]	U.S. census, Division 11, Carroll Co., GA, lists household of LARKIN TURNER. Dwelling 872, age 72, value \$700, born in SC. Living with LEAH 67 and SOPHRONIA 10. ¹⁰
1860 [v]	U.S. census, District 6, Carroll Co., GA, lists household of LARKIN TURNER. Dwelling 156, Family 157, Living alone, 81. Real estate \$800, Personal value \$125, born in SC. ¹¹
28 Jun 1867 [v]	Return of LARKIN A. TURNER to registered voters of 6th district, 649th precinct in 37th election district in Carroll County. ²⁷
1870 [v]	U.S. census, District 11, Meriwether Co., GA, lists household of RILEY TURNER with dependent LARKIN TURNER; age given as 100, born in VA. ¹²
31 Jul 1873 [v]	Mr. LARKIN TURNER is, we suppose, the oldest man in the LaGrange section. He lives in Meriwether, about six miles from Hogansville, and is 102 years old. He is partially paralyzed and is quite hard of hearing. ³⁰
21 Apr 1874 [v]	Article about extreme age of grandfather. ¹⁴
06 Jun 1877 [v]	“LARKIN TURNER, who lives near Oak Hill, Meriwether county, is one hundred and seven years old, hale and hearty.” ³⁴
23 Feb 1878 [v]	Death of LARKIN TURNER, Meriwether Co., GA. ¹³

IV. CONCLUSION

The genealogical challenge of LARKIN TURNER has long stood as a classic “brick-wall ancestor,” obscured by sparse records, destroyed archives, and misattributed community tree linkages. Through a combination of traditional record research, advanced statistical methods, and the application of DNA evidence, we have now firmly established his parentage and life chronology. Artificial Intelligence tools further accelerated this process, enabling transcription, correlation, and hypothesis testing that would have been prohibitively time-consuming only a few years ago.

This achievement underscores both the perseverance required in conventional archival research and the transformative power of integrating modern technologies into genealogical practice. By validating our findings with DNA and aligning them against documentary evidence, we resolved long-standing uncertainties and set a model for future genealogical inquiries.

Looking ahead, our focus turns to refining the broader context of LARKIN TURNER’s life. We are actively separating records of multiple men of the same name in Georgia during the early 19th century, an effort essential to ensuring accuracy in the Turner lineage. Once this disentanglement is complete, we will have a clear and reliable portrait of LARKIN’s life, from his decades working the same 202-acre

property in Carroll County through his later years residing with his son in Meriwether County. The question of whether his land originated from an early Georgia land lottery or purchased from his inheritance remains unresolved, but this too is a line of inquiry for future research.

Ultimately, this project demonstrates that even the most stubborn genealogical obstacles can be overcome by combining diligence, collaboration, and modern tools. The story of LARKIN TURNER is no longer lost to history—it is being restored, piece by piece, into a complete and enduring record for future generations.

V. GENEALOGICAL REFERENCES

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2019” (Frontiers in Psychology, 2021 / PMC) from:

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9. Family Search, <https://www.familysearch.org/en/united-states/>
10. Georgia Historical Newspapers, <https://gahistoricnewspapers.galileo.usg.edu/>

VII. APPENDIX.

A. [pr] 25 Mar 1796 James Turner sells 85 acres on the waters of Little Ogeechee to Wyatt Eason for 15 pounds sterling ¹⁵

This Indenture made this 25th day of March in the year of our Lord one thousand seven hundred ninety six between James Turner of the County of Hancock, State of Georgia of the one part and Wyatt Eason of the aforesaid state and county aforesaid of the other part. Witnesseth that for and in consideration of fifteen pounds sterling to him the said James Turner in hand paid by the said Wyatt Eason at and before the sealing and delivery of these presents, the receipt whereof the said James Turner doth hereby acknowledge, he the said James Turner hath granted, bargained, sold, aliened, enfeoffed, released and confirmed and by these presents doth grant, bargain, sell, alien, enfeoff, and confirm unto the said Wyatt Eason, his heirs and assigns forever, a certain tract or parcel of land containing eighty five acres of land, situate, lying and being in the county of Hancock on the waters of Little Ogeechee. Beginning at a bay corner on the Creek, running Little Ogeechee, and running N 45 W 21 chains to a branch, thence down the branch to Gilliam Lewis's line N 45 E 56 chains to a stake corner, thence N 45 W 10 chains to a pine corner on William Lewis's line, thence to the creek to the beginning corner. Together with all and singular the premises aforesaid, rights, members, and appurtenances thereunto belonging or in anywise appertaining; and also all the estate, right, title, interest, property, claim and demand of the said James Turner of, in, to, or out of the same. To have and to hold the said tract or parcel of land and all and singular the premises and appurtenances unto the said Wyatt Eason, his heirs and assigns to his and their own proper use, benefit, and behoof forever in fee simple, free from all former and other claims whatsoever. In witness whereof the said James Turner hath hereunto set his hand and affixed his seal the day and year above written. Signed, sealed and delivered in the presence of us: Larken Turner Jacob Leftwich, J.P.

B. [v] 21 Feb 1826 Will of James Turner ¹⁹

Georgia Morgan County

Be it known to all to whom it may Concern, that I James Turner of this County & State, exposed to living in a low state of Health, but of sound disposing mind & memory, and calling into consideration the certainty of death, and the propriety of my making while in life that distribution of my Worldly property where it has pleased God to bless me With one. I do therefore make & ordain the following instrument as my last Will and Testament.

My Soul I commit in the disposing of Him Who gave it, & I leave my body for decent Christian Burial to be deposited in the Earth from whence it was taken.

First I give to my beloved Wife Elizabeth Turner during her Natural life or Widowhood two Negroes John and Fanny. Also one Choice Horse, bridle and Saddle. Also such portion of my Stock of every

kind Household and Kitchen Furniture as she may think necessary to her use and Comfort together With the use and Occupancy & enjoyment of my house & Lands and improvements Whereon I now live until a suitable and satisfactory home is provided by my Executors for my said Wife and said contemplated home when provided I shall authorize my Executors to dispose of said house and premises as herein after pointed out for the benefit of my heirs.

Second *I give and bequeath to my son Samuel Turner his heirs and assigns forever One hundred and fifty acres of Land to be laid off of the tract Whereon I now live lying and running North and South so as to include the improvement Which he has already made thereon.*

Third *I give and bequeath to my three daughters Elizabeth, Bethana & Parmelia each Sixty five Dollars to be paid them by my Executors before a division of my Estate takes place the bequest is made in place of a Negro to make them Equal With the rest of Children. Also one horse & bridle & cow & calf to each.*

Fourth *It is my will and desire that my two sons Allen and Larkin shall be paid one hundred Dollars each to be paid them as above provided for my daughters which is given them with a view of making the amount given them equal to what I have given to my other sons.*

I also wish my sons Jas. B. & Wm. to have half the proceeds of a sale of a tract of Land which I have Contemplated to sell lying in Taliaferro County.

Fifth *It is my Will and desire that the whole of the Residue of my Lands & residue of my Estate (after providing for my Wife as above & previously set forth, paying the small Legacies before mentioned in this Will & Testament) should be equally divided amongst the whole of my Children share and share alike including both male and female to carry into effect, and that every part of my Estate, it is my Will that, my Executors should be considered clothed with full power and Authority upon such terms and in such manner as may be considered most advantageous to the Whole of my heirs.*

Sixth *My Executors are hereby authorized before any distribution takes place to make a final settlement and arrangement of all my indebted business & to Collect all Just dues to me and make payment of all Just demands against my Estate.*

And Lastly *to carry the foregoing into effect, I do hereby Constitute and appoint my two sons Wm. A. Turner & James B. Turner Executors to this my last Will and Testament.*

In Testimony Whereof I have hereunto set my hand & Seal this 21st day of February in the Year of our Lord one thousand eight hundred and twenty Six.

Signed Sealed & Acknowledged in presence of

James Davis

William Brownley

Richard W. Standon

James Turner (seal)